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Relational values of nature in EU initiatives

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List of acronyms

- **BESTLIFE** Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Territories of European Overseas
- **CAP** Common Agricultural Policy
- **EGE** European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- **GAEC** Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions
- **LEADER** Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale
- **LIFE** Programme for the Environment and Climate Action
- **proGInreg** Productive Green Infrastructure for Post-Industrial Urban Regeneration
- **SAEGE** Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies

Executive summary

This report analyses how relational values of nature are reflected in selected EU initiatives, indicating how relational framings are embedded and operationalised in practice. It builds on the recognition that EU environmental governance already contains relational elements, even where these are not explicitly framed as relational values. The report examines two examples from EU initiatives in which relationships between people and nature are central to policy design and implementation — the *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030* and the *Vision for Agriculture and Food* — and assesses their relevance for ongoing debates about plural valuation in environmental policymaking.

First, the report outlines a concise working definition of relational values and identifies examples of relational values — stewardship, care, identity, participation, learning, and responsibility. Next, the two EU strategies are outlined and analysed narratively with attention to how relational dimensions are embedded in design and implementation in downstream programmes, projects, initiatives, and regulations. Finally, the conclusion identifies insights and considers their implications for policy.

The following findings of the analysis represent key issues for further reflection by the EGE:

- Relational values of nature are referred to in both the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Vision for Agriculture and Food, even though they are not named explicitly.
- These relational framings tend to remain implicit and secondary to economic and performance-oriented policy logics, which suggests their being interpreted instrumentally.
- Quantitative targets and regulatory measures tend to be specified in detail, whereas relational values are less clearly operationalised, which limits their influence on how policy trade-offs and priorities are shaped.

Introduction

This report was prepared by the project Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies (SAEGE) in February 2026 in response to a request from the Secretariat of the EGE in the context of the EGE's forthcoming Opinion on the value of nature. It forms one of two reports supporting the EGE's reflection.

The European Commission requested advice from the EGE on approaches to valuing nature in governance and across society, particularly in relation to the ethical questions that emerge from how humans relate to nature and their responsibility towards it. The questions posed by the European Commission to the EGE were as follows:

- Which assumptions about the value of nature, biodiversity, ecosystems and of the relationship of humans to nature should underpin policy decisions? How are these dimensions integrated into (economic) policymaking at EU and national levels, and in underlying models used for impact assessment, policy design, monitoring and evaluation? On this basis, what kinds of governance action are required, also with regard to the further development of the European Green Deal and of

what is to follow it, and the EU's strategies and actions in the global context?

- What are important ethical considerations as regards conceptualisations about the rights and standing of non-human parts of nature? Who is best placed to invoke, enshrine, and adjudicate these rights — and on what basis?
- How are approaches that value nature, and human actions with effect on nature, in economic terms to be assessed from an ethical perspective? What are important ethical perspectives as regards socio-economic systems and the need for a global transition to sustainability?

Relational values of nature are recognised in academic debates as a distinct and normatively significant category alongside instrumental and intrinsic values. However, there is limited information about how relational values are embedded and operationalised in policy settings at the EU level. This report therefore examines selected EU initiatives in which relationships between people and nature are central to policy design or implementation, with a view to clarifying how relational framings function in practice and how they may inform the EGE's ethical reflection on plural valuation in EU governance.

Methods

This report is based on an exploratory, qualitative analysis of two upstream EU policy documents: the *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030* and the *Vision for Agriculture and Food*. Rather than selecting a broader set of programmes or legislative instruments, the analysis focuses on these strategies because they articulate policy priorities and problem framings at an early stage, where underlying relational values of nature are employed (albeit often implicitly). They were also chosen as they both shape the design and interpretation of a range of downstream initiatives, programmes, and regulations.

These two documents were chosen from a larger set of documents consisting of the following:

- [Water Framework Directive](#)
- [Nature Restoration Law](#)
- [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#)
- [Habitats Directive](#)
- [LIFE Viva Grass \(Baltics\)](#)
- [LIFE IP Delta Nature \(NL\)](#)
- [The Heritage Trees Project \(European Heritage Awards\)](#)
- [Progress report EU Pollinators Initiative](#)

- [Revision of the EU Pollinators Initiative](#)
- [Vision for Agriculture and Food](#)

The analysis pursued a targeted desk search. Core strategy documents were analysed narratively, alongside selected documentation from downstream initiatives, projects, communications, and regulatory proposals, to examine how relational dimensions are embedded and/or translated into policy implementation pathways. The analytical focus was guided by a small set of conceptual lenses regarding relational values — stewardship, care, identity, participation, learning, and responsibility — derived from literature on the value of nature. These lenses, accompanied by signalling terms defined by the research team, structured the close reading of texts and informed the identification of relevant examples.

This approach has several limitations. The analysis neither relies on a systematic or exhaustive review of EU policies or initiatives, nor does it assess implementation outcomes. This report also covers only a small selection of the relevant academic literature. Focusing on two strategy documents further limits generalisability across EU environmental governance, and the analysis is necessarily qualitative and interpretive.

Conceptual framework

The conceptual basis with regard to values of nature shapes policy priorities, practices, and the trade-offs considered legitimate in decision-making. Because policy may rely on these conceptual fundamentals, ethical reflection on the value of nature begins by making different types of valuation explicit.

Following Christie et al. (2021; see also Chan et al. 2016, 2018), this report distinguishes between three broad value types:

- instrumental (something valued as a substitutable means to a human end)
- intrinsic (something valuable in and of itself)
- relational (a non-substitutable, meaningful relationship between people and nature)

The tripartite value typology

While in the academic debate some authors insist that relational values of nature are a distinct category (e.g. Deplazes-Zemp, Chapman, 2021; Deplazes-Zemp 2024), there are also objections to extending the common distinction of instrumental and intrinsic values to include a third category. For example, James (2022) points to the fact that instrumental values *are* relational values, conceptually speaking: “if x has instrumental value as a means to some valuable end y, then x’s value obviously depends on the relations between x and y” (p. 48). Hence, either the term “relational” does not sufficiently distinguish this

category from the other two, or it signifies something beyond what is already encapsulated in instrumental relations.

One route available here is to accept the second option and claim that “relational” here captures, for example, meaningful relationships that go beyond means-end relations. However, James adds that the term “constitutive value” (p. 47) is actually often better suited to capture what adherents of relational values envision, as is the case with natural surroundings being part of a valuable whole.

Further, in a paper criticising the notion, Baard rejects two broad justificatory attempts for relational values of nature: the idea that all ethical concepts are relational, motivated by some quite excessive definitions of relational values, and the view that this notion captures something novel and indispensable which is not captured by existing concepts like the two other broad value types (Baard 2025). Additionally, in their literature review, Himes et al. identify “fuzzy boundaries” between the three types of values, and especially between instrumental and relational values of nature. In their view, these fuzzy boundaries are not outright problematic, as they might mirror the “importance of context and perspectives rooted in diverse knowledge systems” (Himes et al. 2024, p.32). Still, they claim “being able to distinguish instrumental and relational domains” (Himes et al. 2024, p.36) is important to effectively implement policies concerning the environment. This may also be relevant for ethical reflection on relevant policy options.

However, to sidestep these issues, we will here rely on the claim that these value types are not mutually exclusive, and that they may sometimes overlap i.e., what is valued instrumentally may also be valued relationally, and vice versa. Hence, this brief will continue to build on the tripartite value typology for the purpose of conducting ethical reflection on environmental policy.

An instrumental view attributes value to nature primarily in terms of the benefits it provides to people, e.g., water, food, or clean air. In the literature, instrumental values are commonly articulated through concepts such as ecosystem services or nature's contributions to human well-being (Christie et al., 2021; IPBES, 2019). Instrumental values are most often linked to economic valuation, where elements of nature can be measured, compared, and priced. In these means-end relations, the means nature provides are often substitutable in principle, i.e. it is acceptable to provide equivalents with similar benefits, although it might not always be feasible in practice to achieve or establish these equivalents (Schröter et al., 2020). While instrumental approaches make nature visible in economic and policy terms, they tend to overlook how people value nature through lived relationships, responsibilities, and meanings that are not easily measured or substituted. Intrinsic values are more contested in the literature: they are often seen as attributing value to nature independently of human use or benefit, which some argue makes them difficult to operationalise in policy or economic terms (Dereniowska and Matzke, 2014). They are commonly invoked when ecosystems, species, or animals are seen as valuable in themselves regardless of human utilisation.

Finally, relational values of nature focus on the meaningful relationships people have with natural places rather than on nature's usefulness or its value in itself. What distinguishes these values is that they are not substitutable: a specific river, forest, or landscape matters because of the particular experiences, histories, and attachments people associate with it. Such relationships are often personal or shared, shaped through lived experience, and frequently carry emotional significance which is often considered non-substitutable. A

resident's long-standing connection to a river or landscape, for example, cannot simply be replaced by another site, even if similar experiences may arise elsewhere over time.

It is important to recognise that the notion of relational values is located between descriptive statements or views on the one hand, and more normative or evaluative viewpoints on the other. From a descriptive standpoint, specific persons or social groups in fact value nature in a relational way, or envisage their relationship with nature or natural surroundings as valuable; the notion of relational values of nature may simply be better able to address such social facts. Meanwhile, from a normative standpoint, there may be (moral) values which arise from relationships with nature, or it may be normatively required to respect or develop relations to nature, as may be the case for individuals in a community whose members are expected to view a site as part of their identity (Stålhammar, Thorén 2019).

This distinction also connects with the distinction between agent-relativity and agent-neutrality: the value of a specific place or plant may either be relative to the human agents involved in the relationship, or the relationship may be valuable per se, disregarding the human person (Baard 2025). And this may also be a distinguishing feature with regard to the question of anthropocentrism of relational values, since the view that the relationship is valuable independently from human agents is less anthropocentric. This distinction is relevant for policymakers because, if people are sometimes normatively required to develop relational values of nature and this may be fostered by means of policy, then this gives reasons to choose and operationalise some of these policy options.

Related to this, it is sometimes accepted that relational values are conducive for the good life. For instance, Schröter et al. claim that "different dimensions of [relational values] comprise eudaimonic values, which contribute to a meaningful life worth living" (Schröter et al. 2020, p50; cf. Deplazes-Zemp,

Chapman 2021). This shifts relational values closer to instrumentally valuable features, as they are said to contribute to people's good life (Díaz 2015). However, circling back to James's position, one could of course also frame the values as constitutive of the good life.

Characteristics of relational values of nature and their ethical relevance

Although many landscapes have been shaped by human activities, the meanings individuals and communities attach to them can still be understood as relational values of nature. Common examples of relational values encompass *historical, personal, experience-based, non-commodifiable, and potentially immaterial qualities*. These values often overlap with cultural and political traditions passed down across generations, such as festivals tied to specific places or the symbolic meaning of place names. Relational values are not easily quantified or monetised. Finally, relational values can also involve ambivalent or even negative experiences of nature, thereby reflecting the complexity of human–nature relationships.

In this report, we focus on *care, stewardship, identity, participation, learning, and responsibility* as the prime instances of relational values of nature, i.e., valuable relationships with nature. This list is derived from literature on the value of nature.¹ Specifically, the review draws on the Life Framework of Values (via Kenter and O'Connor, 2022; Christie et al., 2021), which references practices of

care for the human and non-human world, *identity* in relation to place, and relational modes of “living with” and “living as” nature. The environmental economics literature also addresses *stewardship* as a non-use value (Aruga, 2022); *participation* through deliberative and inclusive valuation methods that prioritise shared and social values (Craig, Stevenson and Meadowcroft, 2019; Buitendijk et al., 2024); nature's contribution to *learning* and inspiration (Christie et al., 2019); and *responsibility* in the reciprocal obligations arising from humans' ongoing relationships with ecosystems (Kauffman, 2021).

Concerning the ethical relevance of these more concrete relational values, we should note that individual instances of these can interact, and some may conflict with other relational or non-relational values. Regarding interaction, it will become apparent in our analysis of the two policy documents that relational values of nature can motivate people to care for or steward landscapes or other features of the natural environment in virtue of being constitutive of people's identity. Of course, care or stewardship will often simply be indicative of (or an expression of) these values.

Regarding conflict, the discussion in the previous section suggests that relational values do not conflict with instrumental or intrinsic values on a conceptual level: that is, if relational values partially overlap with instrumental or intrinsic values, it is not the case that they conflict simply because they are these types of values. However, specific features of relational values can in fact conflict with features of instrumental values. For instance, the feature of substitutability of instrumental values conflicts with the non-substitutability of

¹ The research team drew from sources cited within the Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA) “Introductory narrative literature review on the value of nature and valuing nature”, an internal working document prepared for the EGE and its Secretariat.

relational values. This is why experiences with a new landscape or natural surrounding may provide benefits to a community instrumentally, but cannot substitute an earlier relationship the group had with another site.

At the same time, the mere fact that two values are relational (such as stewardship and identity) of course does not prevent them from conflicting. For example, the cultural and biographical connections of a community to a largely untouched landscape or more confined natural object may be part of the identity of individuals of which the group is composed. The values of care or stewardship might motivate those individuals to intervene in this pristine area, changing its status and thus potentially conflicting with the relational value of identity. While policy advice certainly cannot account for every downstream conflict, it can take up potential conflicts at a more general level.

Further, in their review, Himes et al. note that the integration of relational values of in policymaking is currently often restricted to rather broad strategies, and does not offer much with regard to operationalisation. A more concrete integration could help, for instance by helping to adjust to more localised contexts, to enlarge the audience of policy, or to encourage motivation (Himes et al. 2024, p.37). Policy that is more plural with regard to the value types endorsed is hence more sensitive to the particularities of communities it applies to. We will come back to this point in our conclusion.

In the following sections, we illustrate how these values are embedded in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Vision for Agriculture and Food. To determine whether relational values appear in the Strategy and Vision, the research team developed a set of associated signalling terms that are commonly used in policy documents to express relational commitments even where the terms *care*, *stewardship*, *identity*, *participation*, *learning*, and *responsibility* are not mentioned. These signalling terms were identified through analysing literature on the value of nature as well as through joint analysis.

Relational values of nature are often considered to be sensitive to context and culture (Norton & Sanbeg, 2021); thus, the signalling terms are not exhaustive. In some cases, these terms may appear without reflecting a substantive incorporation of relational values, which calls for contextual interpretation when analysing policy materials.

The relational values and signalling terms are summarised in the table overleaf.

Table 1 — Relational values of nature and signalling terms

Relational value	Definition	Example	Analytical remarks	Signalling terms
Care	Activities aimed at enabling, preserving, maintaining, or increasing the flourishing of natural objects, habitats, living beings, or ecosystems.	Safeguards for environmental protection; instruments securing ecological integrity.	Care is often captured implicitly through overall policy objectives and regulatory structures.	protection; preservation; conservation; (environmental) management (European Union, 1992); restoration (Armstrong, 2021)
Stewardship	Responsible and sustainable use of natural resources motivated by concern for present and future generations.	Community or public care for a landscape to enable long-term benefits.	Stewardship may be enabled through ownership, institutionalised care, or governance arrangements.	future generations; heritage; long-term care; strong sustainability (Armstrong, 2021); bequest value (Aruga, 2022)
Identity	Personal or collective significance ascribed to natural objects, habitats, living beings, or ecosystems.	Symbolic or cultural meaning attached to a place or landscape.	Identity often overlaps with care and stewardship, as attachment may motivate protective action.	culture / cultural; personal; place; relation; being part of nature; community; web of life (Klain et al., 2017) embedded / embeddedness; part of community of life; holism; ecosystem interactions (Kenter & O'Connor, 2022); space dedicated to nature; living with nature (Christie et al., 2021); green / blue (urban) space; connection between humans and nature (European Commission, 2020); more-than-human; multispecies; symbiotic
Participation	Inclusion of individuals or social groups in policymaking processes related to stewardship, care, identity, or learning; or enabling access to these values where they are blocked.	Community members involved in a local environmental stewardship project.	Participation may enable relational values but does not in itself guarantee them.	participation; inclusion; experiencing / exposure to environment; biotic community (Kenter & O'Connor, 2022)
Learning	Processes through which people acquire knowledge and self-understanding through lived interaction with nature.	Learning about an aquatic ecosystem through participation in a local project.	Learning may be a precondition for care and stewardship and can foster identity.	education for environmental sustainability (European Commission, 2020)
Responsibility	Felt obligation to care for or steward nature, often arising from identity, participation, or learning.	Obligations of a local group toward a species or ecosystem element.	Responsibility expresses the normative dimension of relational values and may refer, e.g., to care or stewardship.	duty / duties towards nature; responsible

EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

Introduction

The *Biodiversity Strategy 2030 — Bringing nature back into our lives* (European Commission, 2020) was adopted in 2020 as part of the European Green Deal package. According to its summary (European Union, n.d.-a), the Strategy formulates a framework of actions and commitments aiming to tackle the main causes of biodiversity loss. Among other goals, it commits to legally protecting 30% of both land and sea in the EU by 2030. Furthermore, the Strategy moves beyond protection alone and towards nature restoration. Its objectives have since been translated into more concrete policy initiatives — below we consider the *Nature Restoration Regulation* (European Union, 2024b), the *Revised EU Pollinators Initiative* (European Commission, 2023a), the continuation of funding for projects under the LIFE programme, and the EU's implementation of the *Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (Convention on Biological Diversity, n.d.), among others.

Taken together, the Strategy highlights the ways in which human societies are dependent on nature, for example by pointing towards ecosystem services and emphasising the economic benefits in relation to biodiversity conservation. Overall, the Strategy combines economic framings of biodiversity protection and restoration (such as quantified targets, labour-market prospects, and minimum percentages of protected areas) with more qualitative language that gestures toward relational values. While the Strategy does not explicitly employ the terminology of relational values, it implicitly draws on such values in support of its protection and restoration objectives. Relational values embedded within the Strategy may lend themselves to an instrumental reading

because they are not articulated as normative principles that can guide governance choices, responsibilities, and participatory processes. Since instrumental and relational values can coexist and may – as discussed – sometimes overlap, giving relational values a meaningful role in governance may require making them explicit and specifying how they can be recognised and operationalised in policy design and implementation.

Analysis

Care

The Strategy implicitly invokes relational values of care, e.g., when it states that “protecting the nature we have will not be enough to bring nature back into our lives” (section 2.2). That logic is then made more operational in downstream initiatives such as the Revised EU Pollinators Initiative (European Commission, 2023a), which moves from protection alone to an explicit repair-and-support agenda: it frames pollinator decline as a societal concern requiring “decisive action” to address underlying drivers and structures delivery around three priorities (improving knowledge, improving conservation and tackling pressures, and mobilising society and strategic cooperation).

An implicit understanding of care is reinforced by the Strategy's opening, which recognises that, despite existing legal frameworks, “protection has been incomplete” and “restoration has been small-scale” (section 2), with insufficient implementation and enforcement. At the same time, within the Strategy itself,

care is primarily expressed through quantitative targets and high-level commitments — such as the net-gain orientation and the acknowledgement that regulation alone is insufficient — rather than through an explicit relational framing. While this framing points to a duty of care toward degraded ecosystems, the Strategy neither articulates care as a normative principle shaping how humans ought to relate to nature nor specifies how existing policies and governance arrangements might be re-oriented to reflect such relationships.

An implicit orientation toward care is also taken up in adjacent Green Deal initiatives that shape how biodiversity objectives are translated into corporate practice. While not a direct measure of implementation of the Biodiversity Strategy, the *Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive* (European Union, 2024a) operates within the same policy framework and reinforces its objectives by extending responsibility for environmental harm into corporate governance. The legislative proposal (European Commission, 2022, Article 25) references a “duty of care” for directors to “take into account the consequences of their decisions for sustainability matters, including, where applicable, human rights, climate change and environmental consequences, including in the short, medium and long term.”

Stewardship and responsibility

Regarding the value of stewardship, the Strategy explicitly labels farmers as “guardians of our land” who “play a vital role in preserving biodiversity” (section 2.2.2). Immediately following this framing, the Strategy refers to the *Farm-to-Fork Strategy* (European Union, 2020) and the new *Common Agricultural Policy* (CAP, European Commission, n.d.-b), where stewardship is set to be operationalised. In Farm to Fork, stewardship is extended beyond farmers to the entire food system; the framework stresses that “all actors of the food chain must play their part” and that it will address the “responsibilities of all actors in

the food system” (sections 2–2.1), thereby linking stewardship to long-term resilience through the premise that increasing sustainability ultimately strengthens producers’ resilience (European Union, 2020, p. 8). Under Farm to Fork, stewardship appears as a topic of discussion within events such as the EU–Canada dialogue (European Commission, n.d.-a). Additionally, communications on the post-2027 CAP proposal describe a “farm stewardship system” that translates this responsibility into a balance of baseline obligations and targeted incentives, suggesting that stewardship is an ongoing duty to maintain environmental conditions rather than a purely voluntary or compensatory measure (European Commission, n.d.-b).

At the same time, stewardship is framed mainly as a matter of good management rather than a clearly articulated responsibility that has ethical pertinence, which illustrates the potential instrumental reading of relational values in the Strategy. While it assigns duties to specific actors (e.g., farmers), it does not articulate stewardship as a commitment to sustaining ecological elements that cannot be replaced or compensated once lost. Such an understanding would treat stewardship not only as maintaining productivity or resilience over time but also as a recognition that certain ecological functions are non-replaceable for future generations. Elements of this reasoning appear only indirectly (for example, when the Strategy notes that “soil is a hugely important non-renewable resource”, section 2.2.3) but are not developed into a broader guiding principle for how stewardship should constrain decisions and trade-offs. Although stewardship is not explicitly picked up in these documents as a relational value, to a certain extent these findings reflect the placement of relational values in between descriptive and normative views.

Stewardship is also implemented within the LIFE Stewardship project in Spain (Eurosite, n.d.), which links landowners, conservation organisations, businesses, and public authorities in long-term arrangements to conserve natural and cultural values on specific sites. In addition to contractual arrangements and

financing mechanisms, LIFE Stewardship places emphasis on capacity-building and professional learning, e.g., through targeted training programmes such as the European Conservation Finance Bootcamp. In this way, stewardship goes beyond compliance with management requirements and is depicted as an ongoing, knowledge-based relationship.

Identity

The Strategy explicitly frames humans as embedded within nature, most clearly through its opening reference to a shared “web of life”: “We humans are part of, and fully dependent on, this web of life: it gives us the food we eat, filters the water we drink, and supplies the air we breathe” (section 1). This framing gestures toward a relational understanding of identity in which human well-being and societal resilience are inseparable from ecosystems. This perspective can be loosely connected to measures such as Urban Greening Plans, which aim to, among other goals, “improve connections between green spaces” (Bellè & Deserti, 2024). The *National Biodiversity Strategy 2030* in Germany, a national implementation pathway for biodiversity commitments, includes an action area focused on “social norms, social identity, and sense of connection” with nature (German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Climate Action, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety, 2024, p. 99). However, overall, identity remains weakly operationalised and is not articulated as a policy objective.

This limited operationalisation of identity is reflected in how the Strategy frames citizens and communities primarily through economic roles rather than having place-based or socio-cultural relationships with nature. The Strategy largely aligns the protection of biodiversity with economic interests and economic opportunities: individual citizens and communities are addressed as economic agents, market participants, or job seekers — for example, when the Commission projects the availability of “seed varieties, including for organic farming, and to ensure easier market access for traditional and locally adapted

varieties” (section 2.2.2) or frames the planting of 3 billion trees in the EU as “creat[ing] substantial job opportunities” (section 2.2.4). While such measures may indirectly support place-based relationships with nature, identity is largely mediated through economic participation rather than articulated as a relational value grounded in belonging, cultural meaning, or long-term attachment to landscapes. This again illustrates a potential instrumental reading of relational values, since identity is not established as a distinct normative focus. On a smaller scale, some downstream national initiatives give identity a more explicit role in biodiversity matters. For example, the Heritage Trees Project, funded by the government of Flanders and recognised with a European Heritage/Europa Nostra Award (supported by the Creative Europe programme; European Heritage Awards, 2025), treats trees as both ecological assets and elements of local cultural heritage. The project propagates genetically identical descendants of historically significant trees and embeds their stories in public spaces through community involvement and education. However, such initiatives are not explicitly linked to the Strategy, and their objectives and rationales are not framed in reference to it.

Participation

The Strategy frames participation through an explicitly “integrated and whole-of-society approach,” which suggests biodiversity protection as a shared responsibility across economic actors, public authorities, and society at large (“In the partnership spirit of this strategy, all parts of the economy and society will have to play their role”, section 3.3.1). However, participation here is primarily understood in a technocratic and market-mediated manner, i.e., as structured involvement in implementation, financing, and accountability (e.g., through corporate governance and financial systems) rather than as deliberative co-decision-making or grassroots engagement. This is reinforced by a subsequent section on “Measuring and integrating the value of nature”,

where participation is channelled into valuation instruments that measure the “environmental footprint of products and organisations on the environment” (section 3.3.1).

Some downstream initiatives to the Strategy translate this broad commitment into more explicit participatory requirements. At the global level, the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework formulates participation as a condition of effective spatial governance, calling for “participatory, integrated and biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning” that respects “the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities” (Convention on Biological Diversity, n.d., section 1). Participation is mentioned within the Nature Restoration Regulation (European Union, 2024b), which requires Member States to ensure “early and effective opportunities” (recital 65) for public participation in national restoration plans and to document “how the needs of local communities and stakeholders have been considered” (article 15). These initiatives make participation concrete through consultation requirements, yet they do not give affected actors a strong influence in defining a more inclusive or participatory role for social groups with regard to nature.

Some recent biodiversity-linked projects go beyond consultation requirements. For example, butterfly gardens developed for disadvantaged groups formed part of the city of Turin’s living lab under the proGREG (n.d.) project. This project shows how participation as a relational value of nature is socially situated and dependent on enabling conditions; in this case, it was strengthened not only by formal opportunities to engage but also by the provision of social conditions

that make such engagement possible in practice. Downstream initiatives such as BESTLIFE2030 (IUCN, 2023), co-funded by the LIFE programme, operationalise participation by supporting community-led conservation actions, particularly in EU overseas territories. Participation here takes the form of enabling local actors to design and implement biodiversity projects, especially recognising the contributions to biodiversity of “those in remote areas often overlooked by larger funding programmes” (IUCN, 2023, p. 2).

Learning

The Strategy reflects this relational value in the section on “Improving knowledge, education and skills,” which frames biodiversity loss as a challenge that must be addressed through “investing in research, innovation and knowledge exchange” (section 3.3.4). Initiatives such as Horizon Europe missions, the Biodiversity Partnership, and the Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity are intended to bridge science, policy, and practice and support learning across sectors. The Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity implicitly recognises learning as a relational process. Its 2023 biodiversity and education report acknowledges an ongoing “alienation” or “extinction of experience” in human–nature interactions and notes that biodiversity knowledge has historically been embedded in indigenous, local, and traditional knowledge systems (European Commission, 2023b). However, within the Strategy, learning is primarily framed as a means of improving skills and the evidence base for policy instead of a way of fostering deeper relationships between people and nature.

Vision for Agriculture and Food

Introduction

The European Commission introduced the *Vision for Agriculture and Food* (European Commission, 2025a) as a strategic framework to shape the future of farming and food systems in Europe by 2040. The Vision seeks to strengthen the sector's attractiveness, competitiveness, and resilience through an approach centred on trust, dialogue, and shared responsibility across the agri-food value chain (European Commission, 2025b). The Vision articulates several relational values of nature, namely care, stewardship, responsibility, identity, learning, and participation. These values are partially operationalised within policy initiatives — below we consider, for example, discussions on the post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its implementation mechanisms (European Commission, n.d.-b), the LEADER programme, Horizon Europe Mission Soil projects, and Civil Dialogue Groups.

Across the Vision, relational values are embedded through references to place, custodianship, and long-term engagement; socio-cultural linkages; and living laboratories, among other framings. At the same time, these values are often refracted through objectives of competitiveness, efficiency, and implementation feasibility, which can selectively foreground some aspects of those values as they are translated into policy instruments.

Analysis

Care

In the Vision, care is expressed primarily through the framing of ecological conditions as living systems that must be actively protected and restored to sustain food production and European societies over time. Soils, water, biodiversity, and ecosystems are not treated merely as inputs to production but as conditions whose ongoing health is a prerequisite for both agricultural viability and societal well-being. This orientation is reflected in the Vision's objectives for 2040, which call for a “future-proof agri-food sector... within planetary boundaries” that “preserv[es] healthy soils, clean water and air, and protect[s] and restor[es] Europe's biodiversity” (section 2). Here, care is framed as a continuous responsibility to maintain ecological integrity rather than as a matter of compensating for damage or optimising environmental performance in purely productive terms and hence viewed as distinct from more instrumental understandings.

Care also appears in the Vision's treatment of global challenges. The Vision notes the tension between the EU's pursuit of “high global standards to protect universal objectives of environmental protection” (section 3.2) and potential trade irritants. Environmental protection is seen as a universal objective to be upheld beyond the EU's borders: this posits care for nature as a normative responsibility rather than a purely instrumental consideration in trade.

Downstream, care-oriented language is echoed in post-2027 CAP discussions, which emphasise a shift “from prescriptive conditions to rewarding positive actions” (Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025a). Farmers are to receive clearer “incentives to adopt practices that benefit biodiversity, climate, and animal welfare”, including through streamlined agri-environmental actions and targeted transition payments (Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025a). In this sense, care is operationalised as support for practices that actively sustain ecological conditions over time.

At the same time, the Vision qualifies this care framing by stressing that the ecological transition must “carefully integrate economic and implementation challenges” (section 3.3).

Stewardship and responsibility

The Vision most clearly articulates stewardship through its depiction of farmers and fishers as long-term “custodians of nature” and “part of the solution” (section 1) to environmental degradation. Rather than short-term compliance with environmental rules, this language emphasises stewardship as a lasting role grounded in responsibility over time. The Vision states, for example, that “farming and fishing [are] about working with nature,” and that the transition should be “a win-win for both farmers, fishers and nature” (section 1). Working with nature implies attentiveness to ecological processes and limits rather than their external control. The Vision further links this approach explicitly to “resilience for farming for future generations” (section 3.3), introducing a temporal dimension of stewardship that values their role in sustaining long-term relationships between environments and future communities.

The Vision presents a shift toward incentives rather than prescriptive conditions. In this sense, the Vision notes that “[f]lexibility will be extended to

farmers, giving them further agency in designing farming practices” (section 3.1). The Vision thus sees farmers as having an active role and being able to make localised decisions about how to care for ecosystems.

Related to this, in the Commission’s post-2027 CAP messaging, “farm stewardship” is introduced in the context of simplifying and re-orienting the CAP (European Commission, n.d-b). It is presented as a response to criticism that environmental conditionality, as prescribed within the Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) framework, has become overly prescriptive and poorly adapted to local conditions (Matthews, 2025). Framing environmental requirements as stewardship signals a shift towards a localised approach in which farmers continue to take ownership of environmental outcomes. The stewardship framing casts farmers not primarily as subjects of regulation but as actors entrusted with the care of nature. However, stewardship, in practice, still relies on defined practices and controls within the CAP, such as eligibility criteria and control mechanisms. Stewardship is thereby structured in terms of compliance rather than open-ended responsibility for ecological outcomes.

Identity

The Vision describes place, a key component of identity, in stating that rural and coastal areas function not merely as spaces of production but as “an integral part of Europe’s identity” (section 1). This framing values landscapes, ecosystems, and territories for the ways they are lived in and embedded in social practices and forms of belonging. It is reinforced by a cultural claim that the “link between food, territory, seasonality, cultures and traditions” should be “cherished as integral parts of the European way of life” (section 2) and by the call to “re-establish the link between food, territory, seasonality, cultures and local traditions” (section 3.4). This language positions nature not only as an ecological or economic asset but also as a cultural medium through which

shared identities, expressed through culture and community life, are reproduced across generations.

This place-based framing is operationalised within the CAP through instruments such as the LEADER programme (EU CAP Network, n.d.-b), which will continue to be financed under the National and Regional Partnership Plans (Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025a; Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025b). LEADER supports locally designed rural projects and provides an institutional channel through which local knowledge and community priorities can shape rural development.

However, while the Vision's language around "food, territory, seasonality, cultures and local traditions" signals place-based identity, the section more broadly frames identity through "consumers' relationship with food," emphasising that "consumers have an important role to play in the transition" (section 3.4). This wording tends to present identity as something shaped primarily through consumer behaviour rather than as something emerging from shared places and practices. This represents just one example of a case in which the non-substitutability of features of a relationship with nature potentially clashes with more instrumental aspects which are substitutable in principle.

Learning

The Vision places strong emphasis on co-creation, notably through "local experimentation sites" on farms and the scaling up of "living laboratories" (section 4). This frames sustainability transitions as processes that are learned in place-based contexts with farmers, realised through shared experimentation and situated knowledge rather than imposed in a top-down manner. This learning-oriented approach is operationalised, for example, in the Climate Farm

Demo (2022–2029; EU CAP Network, n.d.-a), which brings farmers, advisors, and researchers together to test and adapt climate-friendly farming practices under real farming conditions. It is also operationalised within Horizon Europe Mission Soil projects, which establish lighthouses to co-create soil monitoring processes (European Commission Research and Innovation, n.d.) and via living labs, which are also mentioned in the Farm-to-Fork Strategy (European Union, 2020). However, within the Vision, learning is also framed as a way to speed up the diffusion of innovation and improve competitiveness ("new knowledge and innovations must reach farmers more quickly", section 4). This tends to present learning as a roll-out of predefined solutions rather than a relational process through which actors learn with specific landscapes and ecosystems.

Participation

The Vision frames participation primarily as a procedural means of "building trust and dialogue" (section 1) across the agri-food system, aiming to "guarantee more meaningful and effective participation in the design of future policies" (section 1). While this language signals engagement, participation is largely operationalised as a means of policy consultation through stakeholder dialogue mechanisms, such as Civil Dialogue Groups, and advisory structures rather than a way of co-creating priorities.

Conclusion

This analysis of the *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030* and the *Vision for Agriculture and Food* highlights several ethically relevant patterns in how relational values of nature are framed and taken up in EU policy.

Both documents combine economic policy framings (e.g., with references to opportunities and risks for companies, markets, and consumers) with language that gestures toward relational values. Although neither the Strategy nor the Vision explicitly uses the terminology of relational values, care, stewardship, identity, participation, responsibility, and learning are present throughout. However, these relational elements are largely implicit and tend to remain secondary to economic or performance-oriented framings. This risks their being absorbed into instrumental interpretations rather than functioning as distinct normative considerations and may limit analytical clarity about which policy instruments are oriented toward which types of goals.

Relational values, once incorporated into policy discourse, may be taken up or repurposed in ways that primarily serve economic or policy objectives. This raises questions about how such values are treated within policy frameworks and the extent to which they retain their relational character rather than being reduced to instrumental values.

While relational values appear across both strategies, they are unevenly articulated and, at times, weakly operationalised (as mentioned in our conceptual framework). Quantitative targets, regulatory obligations, and incentive structures (e.g., concrete figures related to environmental protection, plants and ecosystem restoration, or resource conservation) are specified in

considerable detail, whereas relational values are rarely translated into policy criteria or procedural commitments. Specifically, values linked to identity, socio-cultural meaning, and responsibility remain less clearly articulated than those associated with stewardship or care and are less frequently reflected in governance rationales or the design of policy tools or initiatives. While the Vision provides a stronger basis for identity as a relational value, the Strategy — and in particular its downstream initiatives and projects — offers more nuanced statements regarding the value of participation.

Although high-level strategies and visions may not always be the primary arena in which relational values are articulated or given operational form in policy, the degree of precision devoted to quantified objectives (such as targets for area protection, ecosystem restoration, or resource conservation) is not mirrored with respect to relational dimensions. As a result, commitments associated with relational values remain comparatively broad and indeterminate, which may reinforce their more limited role in shaping how trade-offs and priorities are addressed within policy.

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